

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

SIMULATION OF A REACTOR FOR THE SELECTIVE HYDROGENATION OF ACETYLENE-CONTAINING IMPURITIES

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Abstract

Currently, the world continues to further deepen the raw materials processing and improve the technology of petrochemical processes and oil refining and their management. The development and implementation of modern automated control systems using efficient mathematical models, modern methods and control algorithms makes it possible to obtain petrochemical and required quality oil refining products. In the presented article, attention is paid to the problem of developing effective models for one of the most important gas fractionation technological apparatus, namely, a catalytic reactor for the selective hydrogenation of acetylene-containing impurities in the propane-propylene fraction.

Keywords: petrochemical process, control system, mathematical model, technological apparatus, acetylene-containing impurities.

It is known that one of the most complex and important technological productions in the petrochemical industry is the large-scale commercial ethylene and propylene production, which produces a hydrocarbons wide range (for example, ethylene, propylene, butene, motor oil components, benzene, toluene, boiler fuel, etc.), which are a necessary raw material for most petrochemical and oil refining industries.

There is a huge scientific publications number devoted to modeling, algorithmization and optimization of the functioning for the main ethylene production technological apparatuses.

Due to the insufficient equipment (and sometimes the impossibility of equipping) with the appropriate technical measuring instruments, which makes it impossible to fully control the physicochemical raw materials transformations in an industrial reactor for the hydrogenation of acetylene-containing impurities in the propane-propylene fraction (PPF), the complexity of catalyst assessing the state, as well as due to the large number and complexity of relationships between state variables, regime parameters and loads that change over a wide range of the reaction apparatus, it is difficult to construct a mathematical description of this apparatus using well-known traditional methods and models. In this regard, the problem arises of constructing a mathematical model for the hydrogenation reactor using the knowledge and informal experience of the technological personnel. In addition, the variability of the magnitude and loads quality at the reaction apparatus inlet of requires either continuous adaptation of models, or the use of a mathematical apparatus that allows one to construct models that operate in a distur-

ances wide range in the acetylene hydrogenation reactor and are formalized using the apparatus of Lutfi Zadeh's fuzzy set theory.

When compiling a model for the optimal control of the reactor unit, the dependences describing the reactor for the acetylene derivatives hydrogenation should be constructed on the data basis collected during the passive experiment, which are both the result of objectively occurring processes and subjective factors due to the presence of a human operator in the control system.

As you know, the traditional modeling method is the regression analysis method used to identify dependencies between variables. However, when considering technological processes, the inputs and outputs of which are described by fuzzy variables connected by fuzzy connections, it is impossible to apply traditional statistical inference, which necessitates the special methods use that allow modeling dependencies between several variables, taking into account their fuzzy nature. Such a method is the fuzzy regression method used in this article (the $\tilde{E} - D$ -estimation method [1÷3]), which allows, under the passive experiment conditions, to construct a mathematical model based on the accumulated variables values (including fuzzy ones) and reduces to estimating real coefficients $\beta_1, \beta_2, \dots, \beta_n$ of the resulting regression dependencies.

Let us briefly consider the content of the $\tilde{E} - D$ -estimation method.

We call fuzzy $X_0, X_1, \dots, X_n$ variables that take values on the set of all fuzzy numbers $F(R)$.

Let's assume that there is a linear relationship:

$$X_0 = \beta_1 X_1 + \dots + \beta_{n-1} X_{n-1} + \beta_n X_n, \quad (1)$$

where $\beta_i, i = \overline{1, n}$ – unknown real coefficients and let:

$$\tilde{E} = \sum_{j=1}^m |E(x_{0j}^*) - E(\bar{x}_{0j}^*)|$$

where $E(x_{0j}^*)$ и $E(\bar{x}_{0j}^*)$ – mean the entropies of the j -th fuzzy observed value and the j -th fuzzy estimate of the value x_{0j} , respectively, where

$$\bar{x}_{0j}^* = \sum_{i=1}^n \beta_i \cdot x_{ij}^*$$

Below we consider the entropy of fuzzy sets ($E(X) = \int_R \mu_X(x) dx$), whose membership function is also a fuzzy set given in parametric form:

$$\mu_X = N(a, b) = e^{-\pi \left(\frac{x-a}{b}\right)^2} \quad (2)$$

$$\text{at } b=0, N(a, 0) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } x = a, \\ 0, & \text{if } x \neq a. \end{cases}$$

It can be shown that for sets with a membership function of the form (2) the entropy $E(X) = b$.

The criterion for solving the problem of estimating the real coefficients $\beta_1, \beta_2, \dots, \beta_n$ is the condition for minimizing the integral deviation for the entropy of the dependent variable estimated values from the its observed values entropy:

$$\sum_{j=1}^m |E(x_{0j}^*) - E(\hat{x}_{0j}^*)| = \min_{\beta_1, \dots, \beta_n} \sum_{j=1}^m |E(x_{0j}^*) - E(\bar{x}_{0j}^*)| \quad (3)$$

given that

$$\bigwedge_{j=1}^m D(x_{0j}^*, \hat{x}_{0j}^*) \geq h \quad (4)$$

where D is proximity degree of fuzzy numbers, h is some given proximity standard ($h \in (0, 1]$), which is chosen in accordance with the problem requirements:

$$\hat{x}_{0j}^* = \sum_{i=1}^n \beta_i^* \cdot x_{ij}^*, j = \overline{1, m}$$

The formulated problem (3) - (4) can be transformed. It is known that

$$\sum_{j=1}^m |E(x_{0j}^*) - E(\bar{x}_{0j}^*)| = \sum_{j=1}^m |b_{0j} - \sum_{i=1}^m |\beta_i| \cdot b_{ij}| \triangleq J(\beta_1, \dots, \beta_n)$$

and that the closeness degree can be written as follows:

$$D(x_{0j}^*, \bar{x}_{0j}^*) = \begin{cases} \bar{\mu} \left[\frac{a_{0j} - \sum_{i=1}^n \beta_i a_{ij}}{b_{0j} + \sum_{i=1}^n |\beta_i| b_{ij}} \right], & \text{if } \frac{a_{0j} - \sum_{i=1}^n \beta_i a_{ij}}{b_{0j} + \sum_{i=1}^n |\beta_i| b_{ij}} \in (-a, a), \\ \text{otherwise:} \end{cases}$$

otherwise:

$$D(x_{0j}^*, \bar{x}_{0j}^*) = 0.$$

Using the last expression, we can show that problem (3)-(4) is written as:

$$\begin{aligned} & \min_{\beta_1, \dots, \beta_n} J(\beta_1, \dots, \beta_n) \\ & \sum_{i=1}^n \beta_i a_{ij} + \sum_{j=1}^n |\beta_i| b_{ij} \bar{\mu}^{-1}(h) \leq a_{0j} \bar{\mu}^{-1}(h) b_{0j}, j = 1, \dots, m \\ & - \sum_{i=1}^n |\beta_i| a b_{ij} + \sum_{i=1}^n \beta_i a_{ij} \leq a_{0j} - a b_{0j} \\ & - \sum_{i=1}^n |\beta_i| a b_{ij} + \sum_{i=1}^n \beta_i a_{ij} \leq a_{0j} - a b_{0j} \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{at the same time } \bar{\mu}^{-1}(h) = \sqrt{\frac{-\ln h}{\pi}}.$$

Fuzzy regression models of the acetylene selective hydrogenation reactor were obtained from hourly data using the $\tilde{E} - D$ -estimation method.

When modeling, this catalytic apparatus is considered as an object, the which inputs are: PPF consumption - $F_{PPF}^{in}(x_1)$, ethylene content in PPF at the inlet - $Q_{C_2H_4}^{in}(x_2)$, ratio of hydrogen content to acetylene content in PPF at inlet - $Q_{H_2}^{in}/Q_{C_2H_2}^{in}(u_1)$ and PPF temperature at the outlet of the reaction apparatus $T_{PPF}^{out}(u_2)$, outputs are ethylene content $Q_{C_2H_4}^{out}(y_1)$ and acetylene content $Q_{C_2H_2}^{out}(y_2)$ in the PPF at the reactor outlet.

The control actions are the ratio of the hydrogen content to the acetylene content in the PPF and the temperature of the PPF. The consumption of PPF and the ethylene content in it are controlled disturbances. In this case, F_{PPF}^{in} and $Q_{C_2H_4}^{in}$ are non-fuzzy variables. However, the variables $Q_{H_2}^{in}/Q_{C_2H_2}^{in}$ and T_{PPF}^{out} are fuzzy. It is clear that the dependent variables of the obtained models $Q_{C_2H_4}^{out}$ and $Q_{C_2H_2}^{out}$ will also be fuzzy.

The parametric assignment of terms, in accordance with formula (2) for constructing a regression model of the acetylene hydrogenation reactor, is given in Table 1.

Table 1

Parameters of acetylene derivatives hydrogenation reactor models

Variables name	Acetylene hydrogenation reactor			
	$Q_{H_2}^{in}/Q_{C_2H_2}^{in}$		T_{PPF}^{out}	
	<i>a</i>	<i>b</i>	<i>a</i>	<i>b</i>
Small	2.950	8.703	117	0.986
Middle	4.050	0.256	124	4.098
Big	4.500	0.205	133	5.116

Были получены нечеткая линейная модель содержания этилена в ППФ на выходе реактора гидрирования ацетиленсодержащих примесей.

$$\tilde{y}_1 = -0,42177 \cdot x_1 \oplus 0,8513 \cdot x_2 \oplus 1,14775 \odot \tilde{u}_1 \oplus 2,62864 \odot \tilde{u}_2 \oplus 16,13680$$

A fuzzy linear model of the ethylene content in PPF at the outlet of the reactor for the acetylene-containing impurities hydrogenation was obtained.

$$\tilde{y}_2 = 0,77469 \cdot x_1 \oplus 1,54689 \cdot x_2 \oplus 0,08771 \odot \tilde{u}_1 \oplus 6,96143 \odot \tilde{u}_2 \oplus 95,11523.$$

Thus, on the basis of the experimental study and the application of the fuzzy sets theory, mathematical models of the reactor for the acetylene-containing impurities hydrogenation in the PPF are obtained, which adequately describe the fuzzy states of the apparatus under consideration, which operates under incomplete information conditions.

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